

SCHEDULING METHODS FOR UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLE BASED DELIVERY SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The recent Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) approval of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) testing will transform our daily lives. Because of the inherent flexibility, ease of use, and low cost to operate; UAV-based delivery systems will become tremendously popular in the near future. In this paper, we address the issue of cyber-physical scheduling of UAV resources in order to achieve an efficient delivery service. Particularly, to reduce the overall delivery time, we develop a weight-based scheduling scheme, which considers the priority and delivery distance of service requests. To maximize the probability of effectively handling service requests with a limited number of UAVs, we first formalize the problem as an optimization problem and then use a dynamic programming approach to solve the problem. Through a simulation study, our data shows that the service delivery delay and the probability of successfully handling UAV services requests can be significantly improved upon in comparison with existing baseline schemes.

Keywords: UAV delivery system, weight-based scheduling, dynamic programming.

Introduction

Because of the inherent flexibility, ease of use, and ability for rapid deployment, UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) have been widely used for commercial applications. For example, a UAV-based approach to carry out traffic surveillance has been developed by the U.S. Department of Transportation [1]. Specifically, a number of traffic surveillance cameras [2] have been mounted on microwave towers along highways that could be replaced with UAVs.

Recently, both Facebook and Google looked into buying Titan Aerospace, a company located in New Mexico, which develops solar powered UAVs [3]. Titan Aerospace's ultimate goal is to improve

communications by deploying a number of low-cost UAVs. In addition, Amazon announced a plan to offer 30-minute deliveries using UAVs [4]. *Prime Air*, has a goal of delivering packages to customers in 30 minutes or less using UAVs. Google also announced *Project Wing* [5], which has a goal similar to that of Amazon's. Hence, UAV-based delivery systems will become popular in the near future.

Because UAV-based delivery systems are emerging, how to make them work efficiently is a critical issue. Towards this end, in this paper, we first conduct a literature review of UAVs and their applications. We then present the system model for a UAV-based delivery system. To ensure that a UAV-based delivery system can efficiently handle service requests from customers, we address the resource allocation issue. For a simplistic scenario comprising of a single region, we present an integrated weight-based scheduling scheme to assign delivery orders to the UAVs based on the priority and delivery distance of service requests. Our goal is to effectively schedule received service requests and to reduce service delay. For a UAV-based system with multiple regions, we formalize the allocation of UAV resources as an optimization problem and then use a dynamic programming approach to solve the problem. The optimal allocation scheme can efficiently maximize the probability of effectively handling service requests across multiple locations. Through extensive experiments, our data shows that the service delivery delay and the probability of successfully handling service requests can be significantly improved upon in comparison with existing baseline schemes.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we conduct a literature review of UAVs and their associated applications. In Section 3, we introduce the system model for a UAV-based delivery system and present our schemes to optimize the allocation of UAV resources to meet customers'

needs, along with other issues related to UAV-based delivery systems. In Section 4, we show experimental results to validate the effectiveness of our proposed schemes. Finally, we conclude in Section 5.

Related Work

UAVs have been widely used in different areas, including scientific research [6], civilian casualties [7], and search and rescue [8]. For example, in the 2014 FIFA World Cup [9] and during F1 races [10], UAVs were used for photography and video recording. Two advantages of using UAVs in sports are that video can be recorded close to the participants and video can be captured from various angles [11]. UAVs can be used to assist surveillance, including applications such as wildfire mapping, home security, pipeline security, livestock monitoring, and road patrol [12]. For example, UAVs can be used for rapid delivery of medicines and vaccines and to remotely retrieve medical samples from inaccessible regions [13].

UAVs can also be used to enhance space communications. Particularly, a large number of small, low-cost UAVs can fly long missions at high altitudes, thereby enabling UAV-based communication networks. There have been a number of research efforts on the efficiency and security of UAV communication networks. For example, Agogino *et al.* applied evolutionary algorithms to improve the performance of UAV communication systems [14]. Zhang *et al.* implemented a UAV communication network based on the dynamic Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA) Multiple Access Control (MAC) protocol, which achieves a low collision rate and high levels of channel utilization [15]. Olsson *et al.* demonstrated the use of creating relay chains for surveying one target and creating relay trees for the simultaneous surveillance of multiple targets [16].

Space applications can be enhanced by deploying UAVs as electromagnetic spectrum sensors, gamma ray sensors, biological sensors, and chemical sensors. For example, Jensen *et al.* used UAV sensor calibration to improve automatic image orthorectification [17]. Xiang *et al.* developed a low-cost agricultural remote sensing system based on an autonomous UAV [18]. Xiang *et al.* demonstrated a UAV-based remote sensing approach for the slow-moving landslide Super-Sauze [19]. Lei *et al.*

designed and tested a high resolution airborne remote sensing system using UAVs [20].

Given the many applications and uses for UAVs, in the future constrained airspace, it is inherent that efficient methods are designed to optimize the delivery of UAV products to reduce the needed numbers of UAVs.

Approaches for a UAV-Based Delivery System

In this section, we first give an overview of a UAV-based delivery system. We then present our proposed schemes for UAVs to efficiently conduct deliveries. Finally, we discuss other issues related to UAV-based delivery systems.

3.1 Overview

Recall that due to efficiency and flexibility, UAVs have been widely used in numerous areas as we discussed in Section 2. In addition, UAVs can be used to deliver goods. Recently, companies have announced UAV-based delivery system projects. For example, Amazon announced *Prime Air*, aiming to offering 30-minute deliveries through UAVs [4] and Google announced *Project Wing* [5], which may have a similar goal.

We now present the system model for a UAV-based delivery system, which consists of a number of regions and a control center. The control center is responsible for managing and deploying UAVs assigned to regions and routing service requests from users to regions. When the control center receives a service request from a user, it will distribute the service request to the region after factors such as the distance of delivery, region size, and user's priority are considered. Each region houses a number of UAVs. There are multiple types of UAVs, featuring various delivery speeds amongst other features. For example, a high-speed UAV can shorten the delivery time, but undoubtedly is more expensive.

There are a number of issues in UAV-based delivery systems, including the communication system design and security and privacy issues. In this paper, we focus on the issue of resource management of UAVs. To this effect, we developed two schemes: (i) a weighted-based scheduling scheme: For a single region, we develop a weighted-based scheduling scheme to effectively schedule requests and to reduce

the service delay of a UAV-based delivery system, (ii) an optimal UAV allocation scheme. For a UAV-based delivery system with multiple regions, we develop an optimal UAV allocation scheme for the control center to allocate UAVs to regions. It has the goal of maximizing the probability of successfully handling service requests from the system aspect.

3.2 Weighted-Based Scheduling Scheme

In order to effectively handle the service requests from various delivery locations and to improve the service delay for UAV-based delivery systems, we consider a weighted-based scheduling scheme [21]. Different from the First-Come, First-Served (FCFS) baseline scheme, the weighted-based scheduling scheme dynamically chooses UAVs to conduct deliveries based on the associated weights of service requests. A request with a higher weight will have a higher probability to be served by the fastest UAV than requests with lower weights. To efficiently schedule deliveries, we derive closed formulae to optimally assign weights to individually received service requests, which are maintained in a delivery list.

Our idea is to establish an integrated weight assignment, which can cover a wide range of factors in UAV-based delivery systems. We now illustrate the basic idea. Denote M as eligible destinations in a delivery list, which are indexed by $1, 2, \dots, M$. Denote the distance values in different orders as D_1, D_2, \dots, D_M , the priority levels in different orders as P_1, P_2, \dots, P_M , and associated weights of orders as R_1, R_2, \dots, R_M , respectively. It is worth noting that each UAV is responsible only for forwarding one delivery order at a time. Intuitively, the weight should be proportional to the delivery distance and priority levels of service requests. Hence, for a service request with a longer destination and a higher priority, a UAV with the highest speed of those available will have a higher chance to be selected. We define R_i as the probability such that $\sum_{i=1}^M R_i = 1$. Then, for $i=1, 2, \dots, M$, we determine R_i by using $R_i = \frac{\varepsilon P_i + \varphi D_i}{\sum_{j=1}^M (\varepsilon P_j + \varphi D_j)}$, where D_i is the value of the distance field for service request i . Non-negative numbers ε and φ are coefficients for determining the weight value and are in the domain $[0, 1]$. We can use weight assignments to handle service requests with different priorities and delivery distances.

We now provide a brief analysis to derive the optimal weight assignment. Recall that there are M eligible delivery requests. We assume that the requests arriving at a region follow a Poisson process with a rate of μ . The delivery of requests can then be modeled as an M/M/1 system with an arrival rate of $\mu_i = \mu \cdot R_i$ and a service rate of $\eta_i = \varepsilon P_i + \varphi D_i$. With these approximation assumptions, the overall delay of a delivery system consists of two parts: one is derived based on the queue delay model [22]:

$D_{que} = \sum_{j=1}^M R_j \cdot \frac{\frac{1}{\eta_j}}{1 - \mu \frac{R_j}{\eta_j}}$ and the other is based on the transmission delay from a source location to a destination location: $D_{prop} = \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{R_j \mu D_j}{C_k}$, where C_k is the delivery speed of k different types of UAVs. As we know, the weight R_j has a relationship with the selection of a UAV. We denote $C_k = \theta R_j V$, where V represents the unit speed of suitable UAVs and θ is a coefficient. Then, the overall delay can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{overall} &= D_{que} + D_{prop} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^M R_j \cdot \frac{1}{\eta_j - \mu R_j} + \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{\mu D_j}{\theta V}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

To improve the efficiency of UAV-based delivery systems, our goal is to minimize the overall delay of all requests. We have a constraint that $\sum_{i=1}^M R_i = 1$ and can obtain an optimum value of $D_{overall}$ according to the Lagrange Multiplier method [23]. After simplifying the objective function $D_{overall}$, we have:

$$R_i = \frac{\eta_i - \sqrt{\eta_i \eta_j} - \sqrt{\frac{\eta_i R_j}{\eta_j}}}{\mu}. \quad (2)$$

with $\mu \approx \sum_{i=1}^M \eta_i$ and $\eta_i = \varepsilon P_i + \varphi D_i$, we obtain the optimal weight assignment for minimizing the overall delay:

$$R_i = \frac{\varepsilon P_i + \varphi D_i}{\sum_{j=1}^M (\varepsilon P_j + \varphi D_j)}. \quad (3)$$

3.3 Optimal UAV Allocation Scheme

We now consider a UAV-based delivery system that consists of multiple regions and develop an optimal UAV allocation scheme to maximize the

probability that the arriving requests can be handled successfully. Assume that we have i regions that need to deploy UAVs. The total budget is C and each set of UAVs cost c . If we deploy u_i of the UAVs to region i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$), the probability that region i can handle a request is P_i . Hence, the mean value of the probabilities for all the regions that can handle requests is $P = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i(u_i)/n$.

To derive P_i for individual regions, we leverage the call blocking probability utilized in telegraphic engineering. This refers to the case when a circuit group is fully occupied and unable to accept further calls. To derive the blocking probability, we use the Erlang-C formula [24]. In our case, service will be blocked when all UAVs are occupied and unable to accept a request. Hence, we can use the Erlang-C formula to compute the probability that the region cannot handle a request immediately. Then, our goal is to maximize the mean value of the probability that services can be rendered as follows:

$$\text{Maximize } P = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i(u_i)/n \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Subject to } \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^n cu_i \leq C \\ u_i \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Here u_i is the number of UAVs deployed to region i and n is the total number of regions. To solve this problem, we adopt the dynamic programming approach. In the following, we use an example to demonstrate how the dynamic programming approach can be used to solve the UAV allocation problem. As shown in Table 1, we assume that there are 3 regions: *Maryland* (D_1), *Delaware* (D_2), and *Virginia* (D_3). Let A_i be the service request rate for region i . We assume that the values of A_i for D_1 , D_2 , and D_3 are 0.1, 0.2, and 0.5, respectively.

Table 1. Regions and Service Request Rates

Region i	A_i
<i>Maryland</i> (D_1)	0.1
<i>Delaware</i> (D_2)	0.2
<i>Virginia</i> (D_3)	0.5

We assume there are 5 UAVs available to deploy to these 3 regions. The problem is how to assign these 5 UAVs to these 3 regions to achieve the highest probability that all of the UAVs can handle

service requests. To do this, we can compute the non-blocking probability of service requests for each region using the Erlang-C formula. The result is shown in Table 2. For example, when the region in Maryland utilizes 1 UAV, the non-blocking probability is 0.9.

We define S_i as the number of UAVs reassigned from region i to region n . In this example, $i \in [1, 3]$ and $n = 3$. The optimizing function $f_i(S_i)$ is the maximum probability of delivery success from region i to region n . It is worth noting that $P_i(u_i)$ is the non-blocking probability for region i when u_i UAVs are deployed to region i .

Table 2. $P_i(u_i)$ for each region

N sets of UAVs	<i>Maryland</i> (D_1)	<i>Delaware</i> (D_2)	<i>Virginia</i> (D_3)
0	0	0	0
1	0.900	0.800	0.500
2	0.995	0.982	0.900
3	0.999	0.998	0.984
4	1.000	0.999	0.998
5	1.000	1.000	0.999

Hence, we have:

$$\begin{cases} f_i(S_i) = \max_{0 \leq u_i \leq S_i} [p_i(u_i) + f_{i+1}(S_i - u_i)] \\ f_4(S_4) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

We solve this allocation problem with the following steps. In Step 1, we consider only region 3. When we deploy S_3 UAVs to region 3, the maximum non-blocking probability is $f_3(S_3) = \max_{u_3} p_3(u_3)$. In this stage, we have only region 3 and $u_3 = S_3 = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$. The result is shown in Table 3. As we can see, u_3^* is the best decision that optimizes $f_3(S_3)$.

Table 3. Result of Step 1

u_3	$p_3(u_3)$						$f_3(S_3)$	u_3^*
	0	1	2	3	4	5		
0	0						0	0
1		0.5					0.5	1
2			0.9				0.9	2
3				0.984			0.984	3
4					0.998		0.998	4
5						0.999	0.999	5

In Step 2, we consider both region 2 and region 3. If we deploy u_2 UAVs to region 2, we have $S_2 - u_2$ UAVs left for region 3. Then, we have $f_2(S_2) = \max_{u_2} [p_2(u_2) + f_3(S_2 - u_2)]$. The result is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Result of Step 2

u_2 S_2	$p_2(u_2) + f_3(S_2 - u_2)$						$f_2(S_2)$	u_2^*
	0	1	2	3	4	5		
0	0						0	0
1	0+ 0.5	0.8+ 0					0.8	1
2	0+ 0.9	0.8+ 0.5	0.982+ 0				1.3	1
3	0+ 0.9 84	0.8+ 0.9	0.982+ 0.5	0.998 +0			1.7	1
4	0+ 0.9 98	0.8+ 0.984	0.982+ 0.9	0.998 +0.5	0.999 +0		1.882	2
5	0+ 0.9 99	0.8+ 0.998	0.982+ 0.984	0.998 +0.9	0.999 +0.5	1+ 0	1.966	2

In Step 3, we consider all 3 regions and have 5 UAVs available for deployment. When we deploy u_1 UAVs to region 1, we have $5 - u_1$ UAVs left for regions 2 and 3. Hence, the maximum probability for S_2 is $f_2(5 - u_1)$. Then, we have $f_1(5) = \max_{u_1} [p_1(u_1) + f_2(5 - u_1)]$. The derived result is shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Result of Step 3

u_1 S_1	$p_1(u_1) + f_2(5 - u_1)$						$f_1(S_1)$	u_1^*
	0	1	2	3	4	5		
5	0+ 1.966	0.9+ 1.882	0.995+ 1.7	0.999+ 1.3	1+ 0.8	1+ 0	2.782	1

To summarize, the optimal solution for this example is to deploy 1 UAV to D_1 , deploy 2 UAVs to D_2 , and deploy 2 UAVs to D_3 . The non-blocking probability for each region is $2.782/3 = 0.92$.

3.4 Discussion

We now discuss other issues of UAV-based delivery systems, including collaboration amongst

multiple UAVs, UAV to region deployment, and security issues in UAV delivery systems.

Collaboration Amongst Multiple UAVs: A UAV delivery system requires dynamic surveillance and coverage of a target area. In order to provide a reliable service for a covered area, collaboration amongst multiple UAVs shall be considered. Nonetheless, how to attain cooperation and how to schedule multiple UAVs to conduct deliveries and avoid collisions is an open issue. There have been some existing efforts in this direction. For example, Beard *et al.* [25] used a team of UAVs to cooperatively search an area of interest. Guo *et al.* [26] proposed a scheme for achieving cooperative control of multiple UAVs in a dynamic environment. As ongoing research, we plan to leverage existing efforts and to develop a space system featuring multiple UAVs with collision avoidance and high performance.

UAV Region Deployment: In addition to collaboration amongst multiple UAVs, how to optimally design and deploy regions for supporting UAV delivery is another issue. To tackle this problem, we consider UAVs as mobile devices and UAV region as mobile base stations. Then, we can apply the *Demand Node Generation Algorithm* for deploying UAV region in areas [27]. All UAV regions are placed at positions relative to demand nodes and they consider service request rates associated with users' population density. In this case, more regions and UAVs will be deployed to an area with more demand nodes.

A use of UAVs and the required monitoring includes communications modeling of UAVs with multiple sensor modes for site security [28]. Monitoring an area with multiple UAVs could require cooperative path planning [29]. Additionally constraints include dynamic changes between targets in regions against UAVs with different sensors [30]. Together, the UAVs as a system require resource management and communications control architecture [31].

Security Issues: UAVs have been widely used for surveillance and reconnaissance operations because they are versatile, flexible, and generally have a low operating expense. Nonetheless, the nature of UAVs leads to security risks because they are exposed to physical and cyber attacks in open areas. Delivery UAVs receive order information and

communicate with region through wireless networks, which may leak sensitive information to an adversary - those who may actively intercept, disrupt, and/or manipulate data. For example, an adversary may deploy multiple jamming devices to interfere with the radio communications of UAV delivery systems, which may disrupt the effectiveness of delivery [32, 33]. Trends in aerial cognitive networks [34, 35] will require intelligent strategies of UAV robust communications in urban and contested environments. In addition, the UAV can collect information (e.g. carrying high-definition cameras to take pictures), which may disclose users' privacy if the collected information is compromised.

Performance Evaluation

We conduct simulations using Matlab 2013a to validate the effectiveness of our proposed schemes for a UAV-based delivery system. In our simulation, we consider two UAV-based delivery systems. The first system consists of 10 regions and 3 types of UAVs, each with a different speed. The second system consists of 30 regions and 5 types of UAVs, each with a different speed. It is worth noting that regions are located in different locations, handling service requests for region coverage. Because each UAV can deliver only one request each time, it becomes available for the next delivery order only if the most recently assigned request is complete. The parameters used in our simulations are listed in Table 6.

Table 6. Parameters for UAVs & UAV Delivery System

Altitude	1-3 km
Region Number	10-30
UAV Speed	37-92 km/h
Destination Distance	460-555 km
Region Arrival Rate	0.10-0.84

We evaluate the effectiveness of our developed schemes for the UAV-based delivery system by using the following metrics: (i) *Delivery Delay*: It is defined as the average time taken for a request to be delivered from a source to a destination; (ii) *Non-*

blocking Probability: It is defined as the probability that the delivery service will be successfully handled by the UAV-based delivery system.

In our simulation, we generated a number of regions, given different arrival rates for service requests as a function of distance. Based on the speeds of the UAVs and the delivery distance for scheduled requests, we can obtain the delivery time in hours. For each scenario, we first run simulations using the First-Come, First-Served (FCFS) scheme as the baseline scheme. We then deploy the weight-based scheduling scheme to reduce the delivery time. Afterwards, we obtain the non-blocking probability for the UAV-based delivery system. By applying the optimal UAV allocation scheme, we assign different numbers of UAVs to regions. The assignment is based on the results of Section 3. We run the simulations 50 times for both scenarios and obtain the mean value for the evaluated metrics.

Figures 1 and 2 show the average delivery delay of both the FCFS delivery scheme and the weight-based scheduling scheme in a UAV-based delivery system with 10 regions and 30 regions, respectively. As we can see, our developed weight-based scheduling scheme achieves a lower delivery delay. As expected, UAVs with faster speeds are scheduled to handle the requests with longer distances or higher priorities, leading to a shorter delivery delay.

Figure 1. Average Delivery Delay for a UAV System with 10 Regions

Figure 2. Average Delivery Delay of a UAV system with 30 Regions

Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the performance of the non-blocking probability between the optimal allocation scheme and the random allocation scheme in a UAV delivery system with 10 regions and 30 regions, respectively. As we can see, the optimal allocation scheme achieves a higher non-blocking probability than the random allocation scheme. Here random assignment means that we allocate UAVs to different regions randomly. As expected, all UAVs are organized and efficiently assigned for deliveries when the optimal allocation scheme is used.

Figure 3. Non-Blocking Probability for a UAV System with 10 Regions

Figure 4. Non-Blocking Probability for a UAV System with 30 Regions

Conclusions

In this paper, we addressed resource allocation for UAV delivery systems. We first reviewed UAVs and their applications. We then introduced the model of a UAV-based delivery system and presented our methods to achieve UAV-based efficient delivery service. Particularly, to reduce the delivery time, we developed a weight-based scheduling scheme, which considers the priority and delivery distance of requests. To improve the probability of success for handling requests and minimizing the required number of UAVs in airspace, we first formalized the problem for allocating UAV resources and then adopted a dynamic programming approach to solve the problem. We conducted a simulation study to evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed methods. Our data shows that our proposed methods can improve upon the delivery delay and the probability of handling service requests successfully in comparison with baseline methods.

With the future of UAV testing approved by the FAA, next steps include evaluating our methods with scheduling multiple UAVs [36] in both indoor and outdoor situations for information fusion surveillance [37]. The UAV-based systems include package delivery, sensing services, and communications routers. To achieve the commercial interests in package delivery, we will further explore methods for robustness, security, and effectiveness.

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